

FORMING LIBRARY CULTURE – A NEED OF THE TIME

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Annotation: This article discusses the current state of the culture of reading, which plays a vital role in the ideological and moral education of young people in our society. It also highlights existing problems in this area and suggests ways to address them.

Keywords: reading culture, spirituality, family reading, analysis of literary works, cultural speech, text composition, literacy

The 21st century is going down in history as the century of innovative technologies - a period in which scientific and technological progress is rapidly developing, the rate of use of information and communication media is increasing sharply, and sufficient material resources are being produced to meet the demands, needs, and goals of citizens.

The more the economic and social spheres of the state and society develop, the scientific and spiritual potential of people should be appropriate and proportionate to it. The higher the scientific talent, leadership potential, military knowledge, and professional skills of citizens, the stronger their personal qualities: humanity, people's love, patriotism, and national pride, the stronger the foundation and future of our state. At a time when our independent Uzbekistan is steadily taking a strong place among the most developed countries in today's rapid development, the goals set by our people, as well as the growing young generation, who are considered the owners of our future, should be correspondingly deep, clear, objective, and firm. Therefore, in order to satisfy this demand of society - the need for ideologically stable generations, special attention is paid, first of all, to the educational process, which, as the initial stage of maturity, prepares the ground for the personal development of each young person. As our President emphasized, in recent years, a number of works have been carried out to improve the education system and train modern personnel in order to "train personnel in line with the demands of the times and the intensity of reforms".

A base of relevant legal and regulatory documents has been created to carry out organizational and practical work in this area and to establish it in accordance with the requirements of the time. In particular, based on the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 20, 2006

“On the Organization of Information and Library Provision of the Population of the Republic”, the Law dated April 13, 2011 “On Information and Library”, the Decree dated January 12, 2017 “On the Establishment of a Commission for the Development of the System of Publishing and Distribution of Book Products, the Enhancement and Promotion of Book Reading and Reading Culture”, and the Resolution dated September 13, 2017 “On the Program of Comprehensive Measures for the Development of the System of Publishing and Distribution of Book Products, the Enhancement and Promotion of Book Reading and Reading Culture”, aimed at implementing positive changes and fundamental reforms in this area, large-scale work is being carried out in our country. In order to ensure the implementation of the tasks set out in this law and by-laws, the activities of Information Resource Centers in the regions have been reformed in accordance with the requirements of the time, new bookstores have been established, and the quality of service to the population has been significantly improved. Competitions among book lovers have been popularized at the republican level, and incentive prizes have been personally awarded by the head of our state. Young people's enthusiasm for reading has increased.

Publishing houses have increased the pace of printing and distributing works of art in multiple copies to the regions. However, it must be admitted that these places have not yet become sufficiently popular. This means that the population has not yet fully realized that love for books and interest in reading are the most necessary needs in our society. Based on our observations and experience as educators, we would like to share some of our thoughts on this situation .

It is known from the life experience of our people that our ancestors paid special attention to reading books in raising children. The spirituality of our scholars and creators, crown princes and geniuses such as the Great Navoi and Babur, Amir Temur and Ulugbek was formed from childhood by instilling a love for books. Our ancestors enriched the world of imagination and thought, the world of the soul by listening to folk tales and epics. Literary masterpieces - whether they are examples of folk oral creativity or written works - served as the main means of forming in the hearts of our people the qualities of love and loyalty to their homeland, native language, family, and compatriots, national pride, honor, justice and fairness, thoughtfulness and respect, nobility and generosity. Such spiritual masterpieces were read, listened to, and most importantly, discussed within the family or community, and the essence of the works was understood and explained through debates and arguments.

“We need to provide our youth with a decent education and realize their aspirations for science. To this end, we need to develop the preschool education system, radically improve the material and technical base of secondary and tertiary educational institutions, and the quality of scientific and educational processes,” says our head of state. The educational sector cannot be imagined without books. In the educational process, both students and teachers directly feel the need to read books. This is certainly gratifying. However, since students today mainly use scientific literature, textbooks and manuals, their opportunities to devote time to reading works of art are limited. Students are acquiring works of art only to fulfill the task assigned by the teacher in a literature lesson. As a result, it is clear: the reading process is becoming an obligation, not a hobby. A student who does not develop a love for reading books from childhood will not find the strength to read the large works given later, will not feel the enthusiasm, will not express the desire, will only get acquainted with the abbreviated excerpts given in the textbook, and will not fully understand the pathos and ideological and artistic purpose that the author has embedded in the entire content of the work, will be deprived of the true pleasure of works of art, will not feel the true power and might of literature, and as a result, will not love reading books.

There are many negative consequences of low education: a person's ability to think independently, to deeply perceive reality, to react to events, to distinguish between black and white is not fully formed; he is not widely acquainted with national culture, history and traditions; he develops spiritual poverty and weakness; when faced with problems in life, he has difficulty finding solutions, considers himself weak; he has low literacy, cannot fully express his thoughts due to his limited vocabulary; he has difficulty creating compositionally perfect texts and constructing sentences that meet the requirements for cultural speech (such as clarity, correctness, logical coherence, expressiveness, purity). As proof of this, we can say that when we have students write essays, reports, and dictations in native language and literature classes, we see that most students make a lot of spelling, punctuation, and stylistic errors in their written work, and that the level of most students' creative work is very low. Even when analyzing the ideological and artistic aspects of the literary works studied in class and discussing their aesthetic impact, the student cannot express a coherent opinion or attitude .

Undoubtedly, the needs of people will continue to increase, but in any era, the value of spiritual needs will increase and will never disappear. Spiritual

decline will lead to the decline of society, and spiritual perfection will serve as the main solid foundation for the development of society.

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